

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b192
 Date: 26 Apr 2006
 Project: VISURB
 Location: North Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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090242		Start-Up	0.16 kft	128	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
094000		INU	0.16 kft	128	Set to Navigate
100116		T/O	0.66 kft	214	Cranfield
100638		Video	8.4 kft	043	Start FFC & UFC
101943	102035	Profile 1	11.1 - 10.5 kft	001	
102044	102554	Profile 1	10.6 - 4.9 kft	003	1000fpm
102555	103352	Profile 1	4.9 - 0.35 kft	342	500fpm to 500'
103353	105117	Run 1	0.35 - 0.36 kft	334	500', Q1017
105117	105416	Profile 2.1	0.36 - 1.9 kft	317	500' - 2k'
105416	105802	Profile 2.2	1.9 - 0.38 kft	312	2k' - 500'
105802	111006	Run 1.2	0.42 - 0.41 kft	293	500'
111140	112220	Run 1.3	0.42 - 0.37 kft	182	500'
113302	113950	Profile 3	0.40 - 4.3 kft	281	500'-4.5k' 500fpm
113930		Video	4.0 kft	297	Change tapes
115731	120110	Profile 4	4.3 - 0.93 kft	153	1000fpm to 1k'
120111	122329	Run 2	0.93 - 0.91 kft	157	WP87 to WP40
122349	124036	Run 2	0.90 - 0.92 kft	125	WP40 to WP41
124050	130924	Run 2	0.92 kft	193	WP41 to WP42
130924	131103	Profile 5	0.92 - 0.03 kft	272	1k' - 250'
131103	131805	Profile 6	0.03 - 4.8 kft	268	250' - 5k'
131209		Video	0.67 kft	269	Change tapes
131806	132135	Profile 7	4.9 - 2.9 kft	272	5k' - 3k'
132458	132920	Profile 7	2.9 - 0.29 kft	092	3k'-500', Q1020
132920	133810	Run 3	0.29 - 0.30 kft	090	500', to WP43
133821	140347	Run 3	0.31 - 0.28 kft	052	500' WP43-42-41
140347	141116	Profile 8	0.28 - 5.7 kft	357	500fpm
141125	141528	Profile 8	5.8 - 10.0 kft	325	1000fpm
					NEON
143631		Video	5.0 kft	239	Swap UFC to DFC
143804		Event	5.0 kft	225	Abeam runway
144011		Event	5.0 kft	046	Abeam runway
145633		Land	0.15 kft	317	Cranfield
150119		Shutdown	0.14 kft	309	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B192 Track 26-APR-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

VISURB-UK: Assessment of aerosol properties related to urban visibility

Flight No: B192

Date: 26th April 2006

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling of aerosol properties and their effect on radiation.

Location:

Over ocean areas downwind of major pollution sources. Preferred : North Sea from Newcastle to AMPEP point 42.

Weather:

High loadings of atmospheric aerosols. Cloudless skies preferred, but not essential. No cirrus is required for BBR measurements.

Special requirements:

Check the mesoscale model forecast for the position of aerosol plumes before flying.

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometer/Wet-nephelometer

AMS

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

Time	Manoeuvre	Time mins
1000Z	Take Off Cranfield and transit to a point just offshore of the Fenns and perform a profile descent at 1000ft/minute to 500ft.	20
1020Z	Perform a SLR at 500ft heading northwards up the coast until a significant aerosol plume/pollution is detected. Make a full transect crossing of the plume.	35
1055Z	Once the plume has been crossed, descend to 250ft and perform a SLR on reciprocal heading in a southerly direction making a full transect across the plume.	20
1115Z	Once the plume has been crossed, perform a broken profile ascent from surface within plume to map the vertical extent.	10
1125Z	Repeat crossing of plume at various different altitudes, decided by mission scientist.	60
1225Z	Profile down to 500ft in Southerly direction.	5
1230Z	Perform a SLR at 500ft heading Southwards on an AMPEP route towards point 42, until crossed through London plume.	70
1340Z	Once the plume has been crossed, perform a broken profile ascent from surface within plume to map the vertical extent.	10
1350Z	Profile descent to level decided by mission scientist and perform SLR.	25
1415Z	Profile and perform a SLR at 1000ft heading northwards on AMPEP route to point 87.	35
1450Z	Transit back to Cranfield arriving at 5000ft at a 20 degree angle to the runway 1.1 nm to the right of the runway.	20
1510Z	Perform a straight and level run at 5000ft for 2 mins.	2
1512Z	Turn to left for reciprocal run but displaced 1.1 nm right of the runway.	2
1514Z	Perform a straight and level run at 5000ft for 2 mins and manoeuvre for approach landing.	4
1518Z	Land at Cranfield.	

Debrief for Flight B192 on 26th April 2006

Sortie Objective: Insitu sampling of urban pollution from UK cities. BBRs may capture direct effect of aerosol layer if skies are clear above.

Weather: High pressure ridge over UK with light west or northwest winds. Variable amounts of stratocumulus cloud over the UK with bases around 3500ft and tops at around 4500ft.

Operating region: Close to the coastline from 55N in the North Sea round to the Isle of Wight in the English Channel.

Flight patterns:

Subsequent to take off from Cranfield a transit was made to the Fenns (AMPEP point 39) at FL110. A profile descent was made down to 500ft at AMPEP point 87 in the North Sea just off the coast from Norfolk. A route was followed northwest running roughly parallel to the east coast of England and between 5 and 20 miles from the coast as far as 55N (just beyond Teeside). A weak to moderate amount of pollution and aerosol was observed for a 50 mile stretch whilst passing west of Hull.

Nephelometer scattering was around $80 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ and pcasp concentration was around 600 cc^{-1} . Winds were around 15Kts from the west suggesting that the aerosol may have originated from local sources in the Hull and Scunthorpe area and from sources 100 miles upwind around Manchester and Leeds. Levels of aerosol and chemical species associated with pollution fell further north. A profile ascent was made to 2000ft followed by a descent back to 500ft. This revealed that aerosol levels were uniformly low in that altitude range.

Whilst passing Teeside the aircraft moved to just a few miles off the coast. Winds measured by the aircraft were 5-10m-s from the west, suggesting that a plume of urban pollution from Teeside would be advecting out over the North Sea. However, visual observations suggested that smoke from chimneys appeared to be advecting southeast down the coast rather than out over the sea. A few spikes of CO levels (up to 350 ppbv) and levels of other pollutants were recorded accompanied by moderate peaks in nephelometer scattering (up to $100 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$, against a background of $30\text{-}40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$). A reciprocal turn was made to pass along past Teeside. As aerosol and pollution levels rose alongside Teeside, a turn was made onto an eastward heading. However, aerosol and pollution levels dropped as the turn was made and did not rise whilst travelling away from the coast. Approximately 50 miles from the coast a reciprocal turn was made followed by a profile ascent to 4500ft. Aerosol levels were fairly low throughout the profile so a turn was made to head back down the coast towards Hull.

A profile descent was made to 1000ft a long run was made along the coast all the way down the coast and through the Dover Straits into the English Channel. Dispersed pollution/aerosol was recorded past Hull and then whilst travelling past Essex and Kent which was assumed to be from London area. Aerosol and pollution was also strong whilst passing Sussex. Here the winds were more northerly suggesting the pollution was from the southeast region.

A profile ascent to 5000ft and descent back to 500ft was made which showed the aerosol to be well mixed up to the BL top (4500ft). A reciprocal turn was made at

AMPEP point 44 to head back along the South coast and a long run was made at 500ft back to AMPEP point 41. At point 41 a profile ascent was made to FL100 to transit back to Cranfield. A NEON 'paper clip' pattern was carried out over Cranfield runway at 5000ft (4700ft AGL). There was 7/8 of stratocumulus just below (3500-4500ft) so the cameras were not able to view the runway; however it was useful and successful exercise because the 'paper clip' flight pattern had not previously been used at Cranfield.

Summary: A successful flight for insitu sampling of urban and industrial pollution and associated aerosols.

Problems: PCASP some channel 1 noise.

Ben Johnson

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.192** Date **26/04/06** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
110048					cloud base 3000ft cloud top 4500-5000ft Stratocumulus 7/8 and cu light winds
1109		FL110	60		Transitting to operating area Scattered cirrus
101943	start P1	FL110-FL050			Heading 0 towards Point 87
102035	Interupt	FL 105	0		
102044	Resume	FL 105			
102400		FL070			Crossed coast into N sea
102500		FL060			unturrelled Sc 7/8
1032		1000ft	330		cloud top at 4,500ft cloud base at 4,200ft Sc Sc cleared
	End P1 &	-		Just north of Norfolk coast	now half way from 87 to 80
103353	Start P1	500ft	334		mostly clear, scattered sc
1032-37		500ft	330		(Lat 53) Nox high values pollution from Hull & South then
104430		500ft	320		Point 80 wind 260 8 m s ⁻¹
105117		105802		(P2 @ 1 & 2.2)	Saw tooth 500-2kft. doesn't reveal anything.
105502	P1.2	500ft	ATW		2550 very high spikes of (0) for very short periods Going past Teeside
					Concentrations were fairly uniform with height.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.192** Date 26/04/06 Name Ben Johnson Page 2 of 3

P3 ended at 11:39:50
 P4 start at 11:57:31 4,500ft - 1000ft

GMT	Run/Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
105829	R.1.2				Resume Run North towards Newcastle at 500ft
111140	R1.3				Turn back towards Teeside then turn onto Eastward
113302	P3	500-4500 W		Just off Teeside	heading to follow a plume but lost it.
					Turned back westward after after 10 mins and profile up to 4,500ft
					Didn't see any more aerosol so headed south and had a comfort break. Profile back to 1000ft
					Encountered moderate to weak pollution and aerosol neph ~ 70, CO ~ 170. past Hull
					Scunthorpe and down towards Norfolk
					winds West at Teeside, NW at Norfolk
120111					variable amounts of
120111	R2	1000ft	S-SE		SC 4000-5000ft
					No white capping or evidence of sea salt
					for any of the flight
1230		1000ft	S		starting to pick up elevated aerosol and CO. Probably old dispersed pollution from London & SE region, neph ~ 70
1245					aerosol clearing slowly.
120924	P5	1000ft-2500ft			more pollution around 43
131103	P6	2500ft-5000ft			Heading towards Isle of Wight
1	P7	5000ft-5000ft			cloud at 4000ft thick

Soft thick

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.192** Date 26/06/06 Name Ben Johnson Page 3 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132458	P7	300ft-500ft			aerosol seems uniform with height with height
132920	P3	500ft	270		Seeing some aerosol around neph ~ 100 Brighton Pscap ~ 600 CO ~ 150 CNE ~ 6000
1350		500ft 500ft	N		Winds 10 kts 340° reported from Manston. Aircraft show winds light & variable direction
1800		500ft 1000ft	N		Due Due E of London Pscap ~ 600, weakly elevated pollution, neph ~ 70
140347	End P3	500ft 500ft	N		Point 4
140347	P8	500ft 500ft	NW		Heading back to Cranfield with profile climb 8/8 stratocumulus cloud base 400ft, top 5300ft
141100					Cleared BL, increasing rate of ascent to 1000ft/min.
141600		FL100			Transit to Cranfield at FL100
143000		FL100			Descent to FL050 to start NEON 'paper clip pattern'
143500		FL050			Thick sc 8/8 just below probably at 4500ft
143800		FL050			Passing past past runway but cannot see it due to cloud below only a few gaps in cloud
144500		FL050			cloud top was 4800ft cloud base 3500ft

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.192** Date **26/4/06** Name **CLARE LEE** age **1** of **6**
MIS 2

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
100047			212	52°0N 0°36'E	Take off. (1100L) Cranfield.
		FZ110	065		Transit, - 8/8 St W, 7/8 Ci
101943	P1	FZ110		52°42.0N 0°54.0'E	Profile descent
102035		FZ105			} Brief profile intercept } due to air traffic.
102044		FZ105			
102558		5000ft.			changing to 500ft/min
		4700ft.			in StW.
102740		4100ft.			Clear of cloud, but some below still.
103030		2300ft.	215	53°18'N 0°36'E	CO increasing very dense Thin low cloud
103353	P1end	500ft.			
103353	R1.1	500ft.	333		Wind: 6ms ⁻¹ 1280° CO: 522 ppb. neph ~ 500 /cc
103918					Clear sky / thin cloud above - variable 1032 → 1037 NO _x peak
104100			330		2D drop back to 260 NO _x back to normal Winds 6ms ⁻¹ 1275°
104225		500ft.		53°N54.0° 0°6.0'E	6/8 StW above. - very variable Sea: some white capping
105117	} R1end } P2.1↑	500ft.		54°18'N 0°18'W	} CO const. ~ 140 ppb. } Saw tooth profile to check not missing any aerosol above. wind 7ms ⁻¹ 1267°

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.192**..... Date 26/4/06 Name CLARE, LEE... age 2... of 6.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
105416	P2.1 P2.2	2000ft.	310	54°30' N 0°30' W	patchy w above. CO small increase - chimney stack.
105802	P2.2 R1.2	500ft.			wind: 10ms ⁻¹ 267°
105911		500ft.	278	54°36.0' N 0°54.0' W	increase in CO + temp. 2D → 220 max. → power stations ahead. 357 ppb max.
110021					Turn to right to avoid coast.
110038					Straight again.
110420					2D - saw big jump for small time 1/8 thin str above @ ~2000ft. (500)
110735				54°54' N 1°18' W	Chem slowly increasing - barely significant - ^{type side} plane not seen.
111006	R1.2	500ft.		55°6' N 1°24' W	2D increased slightly + tiny bit rain. • Turning right. CO doing cal.
111140	R1.3	500ft.	186		Winds 12ms ⁻¹ 267°
111759					Passing fire on heathland. - no significant increases. CO ~ ↑ 20ppb.
122136					CO ↑ 1250ppb.
112220	R1.3	500ft.	273		Turning left ⇒ back to plane. Heading N to plane.
112622					Right turn to pick up plane leading to East. Having difficulty finding plane again.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.192** Date 26/4/06 Name CCARE; LFE age 3 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
113138		500ft.	East	54°36'N 0°12'W	CO increasing Turning right back to coast.
113302	P3↑	500ft.	283		CO increasing for short time
113402					CO back to 120ppb (background).
113733					Heading to cloud layer increasing rate ascent + gentle course correction to avoid cloud layers.
113950	P3end	500 4300ft.			Turn right, back to S. Profile up to 4300ft for convect break - can't go to 5000ft. due to danger area. CO fluctuating as going in lat boundary layer + cloud.
115731	P4↓	4400ft.			Profile descent at 1000ft/min to 1000ft.
120111	P4end } R2	1000ft.	157		Wind 9ms ⁻¹ 283° CO sat.
120450					AMS seeing small peak. General increase in CO to 120ppb NOx 1 → 10ppb.
120800					Slow CO increase + fluctuating slightly. 9180ppb+

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.192** Date 26/4/06 Name CUARE, LEE age 4 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121759					Over past few mins increase in AMS sulphate 10 level ~150ppb. Winds 9ms^{-1} / 288°
122143					Uet reph humidity goes → 60 → 65 humidity
122400				52°42'N 1°48'E	10 + NOx etc. 10 recording lowest levels Wind 9ms^{-1} 316°
122400				~ way point 40.	~ 7/8 → 8/8 str overhead. pollution is seen in trail CUE = 138ppb
123006			180°	52°26'N 1°48'E	v. small increase in 10. ~148ppb.
123122					10 156ppb. wind 5ms^{-1} 339°
124000					Passing point 41
124300					AMS nitrate ↑ 5 → 6 $\mu\text{m}/\text{cm}^3$ for 2 mins. No other insts seeing anything.
121517					Turbulence
125828					Clouds very low Winds 2ms^{-1} / 266°
130100					Str increases again. → → dispersed pollution from London wind 4ms^{-1} 266° (still light)
130924	Rand. PS ↓	1000ft.			Profile descent + ascent to see boundaries of pollution in altitude + determine highest conc.

Turbulence.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.192** Date 26/4/06 Name UARE, LEE age 5 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
131103	P5	250ft.			
	P6 ↑	250ft.	269	50°36' N 0°0' E	wind 3ms ⁻¹ / 288°
131715					long trough cloud. 10 dips, rep ↑
131806	P6 end	250ft. 500ft.	272		
	P7 ↓				
131900		4300ft.			In cloud again.
132135	P7 int.	3000ft.			Intending to turn around ✓
132458	P7 rec.	3000ft.	091	50°36' N 0°54' W	Seeing ^{small} peaks on turning (clear above.)
132928	P7 end	500ft.	091		
	R3	500ft.			10 cal. 6/8 W some v. thin.
133354		500ft.	087	50°36' N 0°12' E	10 ~ 150ppb. Winds 5ms ⁻¹ / 257° 2D ~ 600 no large variability waves below much less than N. Sea v. few white tips.
133730					At point 43
133946					Drop in 10 to ~ 140 ppb. for few mins
1340					sudden Drop to ~ 130ppb. then const. (small variability) clear above.
1345					10 increase to ~ 148ppb wind 7ms ⁻¹ / 219°

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....192..... Date 26/11/06 Name CLARE; LEE age6 of6

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Whitene

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
134925		500ft	014	51°05' N 1°24' E	10 increase T171pph + NO _x ↑ wind 4ms ⁻¹ / 161° for few mins ~1/8 to v. patchy above. Sea: waves not large at all
140347	P3 end P8 ↑	500ft	358	51°48' N 1°42' E	End at point 41 Profile climb @ 500ft/min towards pt. 39
140927		1200ft			Going through cloud.
141056					clear of cloud through BL increasing rate ascent to 1000ft/min
141528	P8 end	FL100			Transit towards Canfield.
143330		500ft	229		Heading towards Canfield for NEON perpendicular manoeuvre.
143849		500ft			First an fog cloudy to see Turning left. (hard).
144908		500ft			2nd an just; - too cloudy. no ARIES data taken end science, no point in characterising runway T. Circuits + slow descent due to air traffic.
1456					Landing Canfield.

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B192

Date : 26/4/06

Operator and contact info :Doug Anderson dougan@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	CO lamp not switched on until 094000UT
O₃	none
NO_x	None
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	None
WAS	N/A

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 192

Date: 26/04/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:47:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:19:43	35	0.09	152	5												Start Profile 1 from FL110	
10:21:30	100	0.09		5												FL100	
10:22:16	100	0.09		5												FL090	
10:23:10	115	0.10		5												FL080	
10:24:07	145	0.09		5												FL070	
10:24:58	160	0.09		5												FL060	
10:26:01	140	0.09		5												FL050	
10:27:32	270	0.09	166	70												FL040	
10:29:05	370	0.09		20												FL030	
10:30:48	470	0.09		20												FL020	
10:32:39	720	0.09		20												FL010	
10:33:55	560	0.09		30												End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1.1 @ 500'	
10:34:00	520	0.09		20													
10:36:00	500	0.09		20													
10:38:00	700	0.08		20												Noise?	
10:40:00	260	0.09		20													
10:42:00	240	0.09		15													
10:44:00	270	0.08	167	20													
10:46:00	285	0.08		20													
10:48:00	290	0.09		20													
10:50:00	270	0.09		20													
10:51:26	280	0.08		20												End of Run 1.1 & Start Profile 2.1 from 500'	
10:52:29	170	0.09		10												FL010	
10:54:16	250	0.09		15												End of P 2.1 & Start Profile 2.2 from 2000'	
10:56:21	250	0.09		15												FL010	
10:58:01	240	0.08		10												End of Profile 2.2 & Start Run 1.2 @ 500'	
10:59:00	200	0.08		10													
11:01:00	220	0.08		10													
11:03:00	300	0.09		10													
11:05:00	200	0.08		10													
11:07:00	240	0.09		10													
11:09:00	290	0.08		10													
11:10:06																End of Run 1.2	
11:11:42																Start Run 1.3 @ 500'	
11:12:00	Noise		170	20												Noise in CH1	
11:14:00	Noise			10													
11:16:00	Noise			15													
11:18:00	260	0.09		15													
11:20:00	230	0.08		10													
11:22:00	1000	0.09		10													
11:22:24																End of Run 1.3	
11:33:02	200	0.09														Start Profile 3 from 500'	
11:34:06	165	0.08		15												FL010	
11:35:52	160	0.09	171	20												FL020	
11:38:00	260	0.08		20												FL030	
11:39:59	240	0.12		20												End of Profile 3 @ 4200'	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 192

Date: 26/04/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:47:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:57:35	115	0.08	474	5												Start Profile 4 from 4200'	
11:58:55	375	0.09		10												FL030	
11:59:54	350	0.08		10												FL020	
12:01:08	445	0.08		15												End of Profile 4 & Start Run 2 @ 1000'	
12:02:00	450	0.08		15													
12:04:00	515	0.08		15													
12:06:00	600	0.08		20													
12:08:00	700	0.09		20													
12:10:00	770	0.09		20													
12:12:00	710	0.09		15													
12:14:00	790	0.09		20													
12:16:00	625	0.10		20													
12:18:00	620	0.10		30													
12:20:00	560	0.10		20													
12:22:00	510	0.10		20													
12:24:00	270	0.08	475	15													
12:26:00	270	0.08		15													
12:28:00	300	0.08		15													
12:30:00	395	0.09		15													
12:32:00	600	0.09		20													
12:34:00	550	0.10		20													
12:36:00	585	0.10		20													
12:38:00	675	0.10		20													
12:40:00	700	0.10		20													
12:42:00	Noise		476	20													
12:44:00	Noise			20													
12:46:00	Noise			15													
12:48:00	Noise			15													
12:50:00	Noise			15													
12:52:00	Noise			10													
12:54:00	Noise			10													
12:56:00	550	0.09		10													
12:58:00	350	0.10		10													
13:00:00	500	0.10		10													
13:02:00	580	0.10		10													
13:04:00	560	0.10		10													
13:06:00	630	0.10		10													
13:08:00	660	0.10		10													
13:09:32																End of Run 2 & Start Profile 5	
13:11:04	750	0.10		40												End of Profile 5 & Start Profile 6 from 250'	
13:12:43	530	0.09		20												FL010	
13:14:25	580	0.09	477	20												FL020	
13:15:54	550	0.09		80												FL030	
13:17:07	750	0.09	503	1000		3										FL040	
13:18:04	100	0.09		5												End of Profile 6 & Start Profile 7 @ FL050	
13:19:33	645	0.12	626	2000		7	25								12	FL040	

ARIES flight log		Flight: B192	Location: North Sea.	page 1 of
Date: 26/04/06	Operator(s): Joss/Kenn	Resolution:	Gain A: 2	B: 4
Notes: VISURB Flight				

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Sht	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
07:509	START	FLIGHT RECORDING								
10:07:30	Riser	HBB to 60°C								to keep signed in range without changing gain
10:12:40	See	CBB to 10°C								- it's at 27°C when see to 20°C.
10:13	Speed	reverted to 60 scans/min.								- have been @ FH10 for some time.
10:16:40	Rebooted	system to see if scans come back								
10:30	Reboot	wanted if res: is 2 cm ⁻¹ or bigger. Going for 1 cm ⁻¹ so								
	speed	goes to 60 scans/min. 2" unable to configure Michelson								
	comes	up.								
10:49	Rebooted	PC, everything now OK								
	Set up	Macro IR-Fast for 2 9 second's data @ 1 cm ⁻¹ . Worked								
	OK but	returning to normal scan rate of 120 scans/min then								
	old	Michelson config problem re-occurred!								
	Rebooted	PC, now OK.								
11:07	Restarted	flight recording.								
11:23:9		B192@	Csd	71.0	232	18.1	-1929	26.2	CH1	short cal.
11:25:26		B192 P	Csd	71.0	229	18.3	"	26.1	N1 x 2	
11:27:42		B192@	Open	70.3	23.1	17.6	-1906	25.4	Z1 x 2.	
11:29:49		B192 R	Csd.	71.1	24.8	18.1	"	24.5	CH1	cal.

IR-Fast
 1.
 0.
 1.1x group
 55 Angle.
 200 North
 ferrogas
 1 loaded
 - 19secs

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.192**

 Date 26/04/06

 Operator's name: WILSON/OSBORNE

 Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
			PRE-FLIGHT CHECKS					AV = 30sec, BLANK = 300sec, period = 300sec
			Wet neph	→	OK			
			Dry neph	→	OK			
			Lubrication	↘	1.15			RH1 = 42, RH2 = 60, RH3 = 39, RH5 = 69 RH6 = 57.0
								with change in RH due to residual water, $\frac{w}{s}$ seems fine
			with water	→			5°C	RH 5 & 45%, RH1 = 35%
			" "	→			30°C	RH5 = 90%, RH6 = 69%
								Remains well. Brown were seen $\frac{w}{s} = 1.1 \rightarrow 1.5$ (at 70%)
101500								DATA ON. ALL OK.
1018		climb.	10.4	6.3	51.5	↗	34°C	$\frac{w}{s} = 0.75$!!
	PI ↓	2100'	11.6	6.7	65.5		35°C	keep temp constant during profile descent.
	PI ↓	4000'	13.2	31%	67%	↘	35°C	Increase in input RH -
102900	PI ↓					↘	38°C	Set.
103130	PI ↓			36	75			RH5 = 84.5%
103350	PI/R1	500'	14.8	39	76	↗	40°C	Set at end PI / start R1
103850	R1	500'	15.0	39	81	↗	43°C	Set
104245	R1	"	14.9	39.3	87	↗	45°C	Set to max. RH5 = 90%. $T_{in} = 21.6^\circ C$
104510	"	"	14.9	39.3	91.4	↓	5°C	Ramp all the way down. RH1 = 25.8%, RH3 = 27.2% "GT" at 1.8 @ 90% RH

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.192**

 Date **26/04/06**

 Operator's name: **WILSON / OSBORNE**

 Page **2** of **6**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
								humidogram 'flat' @ ^{RH=} 65-70%
105230			14.5			↗	45°C	Set to min. during sawtooth.
100000		500'	15.0	37.3	90.6	↓	5°C	set to min. for final RAMP DOWN
110700	R2.2	500'	14.9	42.5	56.6	↗	30°C	GFC 1.7 → 2.0 @ 90% RH
110910						↗	35°C	(Change at T _{po} = 19°C) RAMP UP.
111040	ir turn	500'	14.8	44	82	↗	40°C	GFC of 4.5 @ 25% definite peak
111315		500'	15.0	42.5	88	↗	45°C	Set to MAX T ₄₂₀
111626		500'	14.9	42.5	91.0	↓	5°C	RAMP Down to min T ₄₂₀ . 60 to 80 90.
112335		500'	14.7	38.0	54.2	↗	45°C	Set to max temp. ready for plume search by.
113039		500'	14.8	37.6	90.3	↓	5°C	RAMP Down. CANCELLED FOR CLIMB.
113330	R2.2	500' ↗	14.5	35.6	71.3	↗	45°C	RAMP UP FOR CLIMB.
114100						↓	45°C	RH5 close to 100%.
114500		4200'	15.0	29.2	90.5	↓	40°C	down for safety.
120000	↓	↓						GFC = 1.75 @ ~88% RH.
120150	R2.1	1000'	14.4	34.1	87.4	↗	45°C	take to MAX to start RAMP DOWN.
120405	R2.1	1000'	14.4	34.1	94.5	↓	5°C	Set to min for final RAMP Down. Fairly nice
121500	"	1000'	14.5	35.7	50.6	↗	45°C	Set to MAX for RAMP UP. humidogram.
122326	"	"	15.5	35.0	84.6	↓	5°C	Set to min (previously dropped to 40°C to stop 100% RH)
123040	"	"	13.9	35.4	49.8	↗	43°C	Set to 43°C

 5
4
3
2
1

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.192**.....

 Date 26/04/06.....

 Operator's name: WILSON/OSBORNE.....

 Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
12363	R2.1	1000'	15.3	40.9	86.8	→	43°C	RHS = 97.5% GF ~ 1.55 → 1.60 Steady, well as high as previously
12430		1000'	14.9			↓	5°C	set to MIN RAMP.
12505	"	1000'	14.8	40.9	53.5	↗	43°C	set to 43°C Ramp up RHS = 48.9% at start of jump = humidity at (165% and 82%)
13005	"	"	14.7	47.4	91.2	→	43°C	Steady reading at high RH RHS = 96.8% (GF ~ 1.75)
13030	"	"	14.8	48.4	92.8	↓	5°C	Set to MIN RAMP Down.
13135	P	250' ↗	14.9	45.5	56.4	↗	43°C	set to 43°C (not quite max temp)
1318								bit 100% RH on RHS → condensation (droplets)? jump GF samples → justs thru cloud (500') as well.
132940		500"	14.4	44.5	93.9	→	5°C	set to min ramp.
134206		500"	14.3	51.3	54.2	↗	42°C	
134654			16.4	52.3	89.3			flow to 16.4 to avoid saturation water temp 42°C
1								RHS (pre wet neph) 98%.
135144		500	14.6	47.1	91	↘	5°C	ramp to min. bit bumpy here.
140204		500"	14.4	44.2	50.8	↗	42°C	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	26/4/06	Flight	B192	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Bowles		Campaign	VISURB			
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield			

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						X	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						X	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						X	
FERA on	at time					07:32	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	17.1°C	Ch	17.1°C	Ch18	16.8°C	
Temperature controller set points		54.0°C	17	58.0°C	-20	40.0°C	
MARSS CPU on	at time					07:35	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289.7	Cold	285.5			
Target heating						X	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X	
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					07:45	
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						X
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	08:30		
Brightness temps 'sensible'	Yes					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.59	Cold	287.63	
	Deimos:	Hot	NA	Cold	NA	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	42.34	34.55	38.11	40.59	42.48	

Power changeover

Headset on before start					
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.				
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)					
Exit Deimos Software (x)					
POWER CHANGEOVER					
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton				
Restart Deimos Software					
System running again	at time				

B192 26/04/06 IR Camera log.

Joss Kent

Pre flight cal.

08:35:05	Temp = 17°C
08:36:05	17°C
08:37:05	17°C
08:38:05	18°C
09:00:52	Temp = 61°C.
09:01:52	61°C.
09:02:52	61°C.
09:03:52	62°C
09:04:52	62°C

Flight Para.

Cloudy!

Hairpin manoeuvre

Time

leg 1
leg 2.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 192** Date: 26th April 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	N
" Red	Y	CVI	N
" Silicon	Y		
" SHIMS	N	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
" Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
" Silicon	Y	Filters	N
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	Y		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	Y
SWS	N	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B192

Date: 26 April 2006

Instruments

1. Nevzorov – Cover windows and screws missing for calibration constant selector panels for both TWC and LWC Control Units
2. Radar Altimeter – reading 0 on HORACE, 4094 on DRS between 5k' and 500',. Reset Port Aft DLU then okay.
3. FWVS started up okay on preflight. Sortie all at low level and dewpoint didn't go below -15°C so data all 0°C .
4. Flight Manager's pc locked up when updating Fltsumm, rebooted then okay.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom Calls

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B192:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing
IR Camera Processing log	
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

3 x Upward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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